

Interview Guide

Human-AI Collaboration for Decision-Making in Agile Sprint Planning

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Part 1: Background (approximately 8 minutes)

1. Can you tell me about your current role and how long you have been working in Agile teams?
2. Walk me through how your team runs a typical sprint planning session: who is involved, how long it takes, and how you reach the final commitment.
3. What are the most common difficulties your team faces during sprint planning?
4. Does your team use any AI tools to support sprint planning decisions? If yes, what does that look like in practice?
[If no AI experience: “Has AI come up in any conversation about your planning process, even if not adopted yet?”]

Part 2: Vignette Scenarios (approximately 12 minutes)

Do not tell participants what you are looking for. Read each scenario naturally and let them talk.

Vignette A: Anchoring Bias

Read aloud: “Your team is in sprint planning. An AI tool has analysed your backlog and past velocity data and recommends committing to 42 story points this sprint. Your team’s average over the last five sprints has been 34 points. The AI tool explains that three similar stories were completed faster than expected recently, which is why it suggests a higher commitment.”

5. What would you and your team do with this recommendation? Accept it, adjust it, or ignore it? Walk me through your thinking.
6. What information would you need before feeling confident making a decision here?
7. If your team’s discussion started revolving around the number 42 rather than your usual 34, would that concern you? Why or why not?
8. Who would have the most influence over the final decision: the AI tool recommendation, the Scrum Master, the developers, or someone else?

Vignette B: Algorithm Aversion

Read aloud: “The same AI tool flags that a story your team has already agreed to include this sprint will likely take 60% longer than estimated, based on similar past stories. The developer assigned to that story disagrees. They say they know this part of the codebase well and are confident in the original estimate.”

9. How would your team handle this? Side with the AI tool, the developer, or find a middle ground?
10. Have you ever been in a situation where a tool’s recommendation conflicted with a team member’s judgement? What happened?
11. What would make you more willing to trust the AI tool’s warning in this case?

Part 3: Trust (approximately 10 minutes)

12. When you receive a recommendation from an AI tool during planning, what makes you trust it enough to act on it?
13. Can you describe a specific time when you trusted an AI tool recommendation and it turned out to be wrong? How did that change how you used the tool afterwards?
[If no AI experience: “What would make you trust or distrust an AI tool recommendation? What would it need to show you?”]
14. How important is it that an AI tool explains its reasoning, not just the output but why it made that recommendation?
15. Is there any planning decision you would never delegate to an AI tool, no matter how accurate it was? What and why?
16. What would an AI tool need to show you, in terms of transparency, track record, or explanation, before you felt comfortable letting it handle a planning decision without your direct review?
17. If you imagine sprint planning where AI tools and humans work together well, what does that actually look like? Who does what?

Closing

18. Is there anything about AI in sprint planning that you think researchers typically miss or get wrong?